

Multilevel management of irregular migration and return in Italy: new insights and data

Iraklis Dimitriadis

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Abbreviations

ASGI Association for Juridical Studies on Immigration

AVRR Assisted Voluntary Returns and Reintegration

CPR Immigration Removal Centres

EUAA European Union Agency for Asylum

EURCAP (European Readmission Capacity Building Facility)

FRONTEX European Border and Coast Guard Agency

GNPL National Guarantor for the rights of detained persons

MoU Memorandum of Understanding

IOM International, United Nations Organisation for Migration

OTL Order to Leave

TCN Third-country national

Key Messages

- There is a need to develop an online database related to migration issues by the Ministry of the Interior and provide public access.
- There is a need to align definitions and common indicators between the Italian Ministry of the Interior, Eurostat, and other data providers. When alignment is not possible, details on possible correspondence between indicators at the national, European, or local level are useful.
- Improvement of metadata provided by the Eurostat database is necessary. The frequency of data collection should be reported.
- Challenges in data collection and monitoring of irregular migration and return management arise from continuous law changes, the possibility of reiterating a negative decision on asylum and an OTL, evolving vulnerabilities of people subject to return, and discretionary practices among institutional actors in dealing with OTLs (Orders to Leave).
- Alternative measures to administrative detention should be increasingly applied.
- Informal diplomacy should be converted into a more standardized instrument of collaboration between national and third-country authorities, especially where bilateral agreements are not in place.
- The content of bilateral agreements on return should be made public. Data should be produced on bilateral agreements.
- The reliance of the labour market on irregularly staying migrant workers challenges the implementation of return policies.
- Frequent regularisation programs for irregularly staying migrants and the complexity of bureaucratic procedures further complicate the management of irregular migration.
- People detained in immigration removal centres need access to Assisted Voluntary Returns and Reintegration schemes.
- Assistance for return should also be provided to those who have received an OTL (Order to Leave).

1. Irregular migration and return in Italy: legal framework and practices

According to Law 40/1998 (also known as the Turco-Napolitano law, *Testo Unico sull'Immigrazione DLgs. 246-1998*)¹, illegal immigration (*immigrazione clandestina*) is considered the offence that involves a foreigner entering Italy not through designated border crossing points and without a valid passport or equipollent document or visa. It also includes foreigners who remain in Italy without a residence permit or any kind of authorisation for reasons such as study, tourism, business, or family visits (Law 68/2007). Therefore, individuals whose asylum applications have been rejected, those whose residence permits or visas have expired², or those who enter Italy without applying for international protection and do not have a legal ground to stay are considered irregular migrants. Under these conditions, an irregular migrant must be ordered to leave Italian territory (Law 40/1998).

However, return as a policy aimed to contrast irregular entry and stay has been often characterised by failure, according to previous research. Leerkes and Van Houte (2020) argue that the lack of law implementation is reflected in the return rate for individuals not who have not received international protection. From 2013 to 2017, this rate in Italy was 5.3%, whereas in the Netherlands it was 43.8%, 31.4% in Norway, and 19.8% in France. In this respect, it has been argued that the demand for migrant labour has countered measures to return irregular migrants in Italy. In other words, the interests of employers (including families) have traditionally generated a high number of migrants working in the undeclared economy without regular legal status (Dimitriadis, 2023), indicating a limited interest to enforce irregular migrants' return.

Considering another measure to counter irregular migration, it should be noted that Italian governments have enabled access to legal status through massive regularisation programmes³. The most recent initiative that provided irregular migrant workers with legal status was in 2020 (Bonizzoni and Artero 2023; Bonizzoni and Hajer, 2022). This was an employment-based regularisation programme that concerned workers who had been previously employed in the domestic (including care activities) and agriculture sectors⁴. On the one hand, access to regular status was possible through employers: those who had an already established relationship with an undocumented or legally precarious migrant (e.g., asylum seeker), or those willing to start a new employment relationship could apply for the regularisation of the interested workers. On the other hand, migrants whose residence permits had expired and who could provide proof that they had been employed (formally or informally) in one of the forementioned sectors could apply for themselves. This procedure also involved civil society organisations (e.g., pro-migrant NGOs, trade unions) and professionals (e.g., lawyers), as both migrants and employers experienced difficulties while applying for regularisation due to the complex and, at times, unclear bureaucratic requirements.

In this context, it is of particular interest to examine how the arrival of asylum seekers has shaped irregular migration and return policies in Italy. As one of the main EU entry points for asylum seekers during the 2010s, Italy dealt with high numbers of irregular migrants who failed to access international protection or any other type of legal status. In this respect, recent legislative measures are considered to have affected irregular migration and, therefore, orders to leave (henceforth OTLs). These laws also introduced a series of amendments in relation to different aspects of return policies. In particular:

¹ The Turco-Napolitano Act, no. 40 (later Consolidated Act no. 286/1998) was introduced as the first complete piece of legislation concerning the status of immigrants in Italy.

² Those whose residence permit expires and apply for renewal receive a temporary authorisation to stay.

³ Until 2012, there were 6 main regularisation programmes enabling the regularisation of thousands of people (118,349 in 1986; 234,841 in 1989; 220,000 in 1998; 647,000 in 2002; 220,000 in 2009; 137,000 applications in 2012) (ILO 2022).

⁴ According to the Ministry of the Interior, this scheme had enabled some 132,000 migrants to access legal status by June 2023, whereas 36,000 requests were still pending as of September 2023.

- Law 13/2017 (also known as Minniti-Orlando decree) aimed to expedite administrative and judicial procedures related to international protection and abolished the possibility to appeal a negative asylum decision to the Court of Appeal (second instance). This means that a decision on asylum may only be appealed at two of the three jurisdictional levels, namely first instance (Civil Court) and the third instance (Supreme Court of Cassation). This law also expanded the number of pre-removal detention centres in every region of the country. Overall, this law is considered a response to the prominence of asylum-seeking in political debates following peaks of arrivals in 2015 and 2016. In 2017, then Minister of the Interior Minniti declared⁵ that rising pressure from local communities (e.g., mayors, local authorities) concerned about asylum management pushed the government to introduce the law in order to expedite asylum procedures, as the asylum system could not absorb more asylum seekers.
- Law 132/2018 (also known as Salvini decree I) significantly restricted the possibility of receiving humanitarian protection status (provided by Law 40/1998 art. 5(6))⁶, thereafter limiting it to those facing serious health problems, coming from countries suffering natural disasters, or victims of violence/abuse. This was one of the restrictive measures against immigration introduced by then Minister of the Interior Salvini, reflecting a tougher stance towards asylum seekers adopted by the coalition between the Five Star Movement (*Movimento 5 Stelle, M5S*) and the right-wing *Lega* party at that time (Dimitriadis and Ambrosini, 2024). The rationale behind this provision was that individuals who were not eligible for either refugee status or subsidiary protection were abusing humanitarian protection. This law also extended the time limit for administrative detention from 90 to 180 days for those who received an OTL and provided more funds for returns (reinforced by Law 53/2019, also known as Salvini decree II).
- Law 130/2020 (also known as Lamorgese decree) broadened the grounds under which one could access humanitarian protection, introducing a new two-year special protection permit eligible for conversion to a work permit. This applies to those who cannot access the two forms of international protection (refugee status and subsidiary protection) (GNPL, 2023a, p. 142), but can demonstrate effective family ties in a specific territory and social integration (knowledge of language, employment). This law also provided for the possibility to access a residence permit for those within the following categories: calamity; elective residence modifies the special protection status restrictively, allowing it only for those whose fundamental rights might be at risk upon return. Reference to one's right to private and family life (social ties and integration, introduced by Law 130/2020) has been removed. Second, this law provides for the opening of 12 new CPRs (one in each region, see also page 13)⁷, and increases funds for scaling up Immigration Removal Centres (henceforth CPRs): from €5,39 million in 2023 to €14,39 million in 2024. Third, new forms of detention at the borders are planned for asylum seekers. The new provision introduces the possibility to detain asylum seekers who have been stopped for evading border controls or those from countries that Italy considers "safe", if they do not have a passport or do not provide any financial guarantee. Safe countries of origin now include Albania, Algeria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Cape Verde, Ivory Coast, Gambia, Georgia, Ghana, Kosovo, Northern Macedonia, Morocco, Montenegro, Nigeria, Senegal, Serbia and Tunisia⁸. Fourth, an OTL can be issued when authorities find out that people lie about their age, claiming to be under 18 (on the grounds of the offense of false declaration of

⁵https://www.repubblica.it/politica/2017/08/29/news/minniti_sui_migranti_ho_temuto_per_la_tenuta_democratica_paese_-174164861/

⁶ Humanitarian protection is a residual status granted to individuals who cannot access legal status on grounds of concrete risk of being persecuted or seriously harmed in their country of origin. Appeals for humanitarian reasons may concern people who suffered psychological violence or physical violence during their migration journey, or mothers who would face serious problems if they were to return, for instance.

⁷ [https://roma.corriere.it/notizie/cronaca/23_settembre_24/migranti-ecco-le-nuove-regole-cpr-fondi-di-garanzia-e-centri-per-chi-arriva-da-paesi-sicuri-e970e52e-c485-4715-b6bd-5edecb9cfxlk.shtml#:~:text=Attualmente%20sul%20territorio%20nazionale%20ci,\(a%20Macomer\)%20e%20Milano](https://roma.corriere.it/notizie/cronaca/23_settembre_24/migranti-ecco-le-nuove-regole-cpr-fondi-di-garanzia-e-centri-per-chi-arriva-da-paesi-sicuri-e970e52e-c485-4715-b6bd-5edecb9cfxlk.shtml#:~:text=Attualmente%20sul%20territorio%20nazionale%20ci,(a%20Macomer)%20e%20Milano)

⁸ Since May 7, 2024, Bangladesh, Cameroon, Colombia, Egypt, Peru and Sri Lanka are considered safe countries as well.

personal data). Fifth, this law increases the maximum period of detention from 120 to 135 days. Overall, this law was introduced by the newly elected right-wing government coalition in 2022, which placed “cracking down on illegal immigration” high on its agenda⁹.

Overall, it can be deduced that the ideological positioning of government coalitions seems to be the most plausible factor shaping the expansion and restriction of legislation regarding humanitarian permits. In interpreting the grounds for international protection more broadly and considering the integration path of asylum seekers as a key requirement for granting legal status, center-left government coalitions, on the one hand, appeared to be more inclusive. However, a significant exception has been the abolition of the possibility to appeal a negative asylum decision at second instance, due to the increasing numbers of arrivals in 2015 and 2016. On the other hand, center right-wing and populist government coalitions promoted restrictive policies reflecting their arguments about contrasting irregular economic migration, as they framed the majority of new arrivals as economic migrants trying to cheat asylum procedures.

Return of Irregular Migrants and OTLs

An irregular migrant is required to return to their country of origin, a transit country, or a third country (i.e., country of return) based on an administrative or judicial act that adheres to “common standards and procedures to be applied in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals”, as regulated by Directive 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008. The overall regulation on the removal of irregular migrants from the Italian territory is provided for in Legislative Decree No. 286 of 25 July 1998 (Consolidated Act of Provisions concerning immigration and the condition of third-country nationals)¹⁰ (GNPLa, 2023).

Returning an individual to a State may include expulsion and border rejection¹¹. Different authorities can issue an OTL, such as Prefectures, the Ministry of the Interior, local police authorities (*Questura*) and judicial authorities (Table 1). As for expulsion, recipients of an OTL can include: a) those who have lost, missed or did not renew their residence permit; b) rejected asylum seekers; c) those convicted of certain crimes. Regarding border rejection, return can concern refusal of entry at the border that can be immediate or deferred. In other words, an OTL can be issued for third-country nationals (TCNs) who enter Italy eluding border

⁹ <https://foreignpolicy.com/2023/10/24/italy-immigration-right-wing-meloni-migrant-crisis/>

¹⁰ The Return Directive was transposed into Italian law by Decree-Law No. 89 of 23 June 2011 (converted with amendments into Law No. 129 of 2 August 2011).

¹¹ According to Law 40/1998, deportation applies to people who enter the national territory outside the designated border crossings, that is, by crossing maritime and land borders at locations not manned by the border police. Such individuals are turned away with an escort to the border, as ordered by the Police Commissioner. This means that the person has entered Italian territory without authorization, avoiding border controls, but was stopped while entering or immediately after crossing the borders (immediately after meaning within 10 km from the land border line and up to 5 km from the shore towards the interior).

If the foreigner intends to apply for asylum, they must do so when stopped at the border crossing, or if there is no nearby border crossing, they must apply directly at the immigration office of the competent Police Headquarters.

A border crossing is understood to be any checkpoint manned by the police. The control carried out near border crossings is different from that conducted along the borders. In Italy, there are 257 external border crossings. If a foreigner arrives at the border without a passport or valid travel document, and without the necessary visa, or if an OTL has been issued, the carrier that brought the foreigner to the border is required to immediately take charge of them and return them to their country of origin or to the country that issued the travel document in the foreigner's possession.

controls and were arrested by the police after crossing the border (immediate) or when admitted for being in need of public rescue (deferred rejection)¹².

Table 1 – Types of OTLs (source: ASGI, 2016; elaboration by Iraklis Dimitriadis)

Authority	Case
Prefect	For irregular migrants stopped by the police and identified at the local Police Headquarters Immigration Offices for: a. Irregular entrance in Italy o in the Schengen Area b. Irregular stay in Italy c. Reasons connected to social risks ¹³ d. Those who failed to comply with an OTL issued by the Police Authority e. Implementation of an OTL issued by another EU country
Minister of the Interior	Irregular migrants who are considered dangerous for: a. State security or public order reasons b. Possible terroristic acts
Head of local police authority (Questore)	a. Border rejection, for those stopped at the borders without valid documents or unable to prove to have the sufficient financial guarantees b. Deferred rejection
Judiciary (Courts)	When return is considered as: a. A security measure b. An alternative sanction sentence (see page 15) c. An alternative to detention

The general rule is that the Prefect (representative of the national government across the Italian territory, under the Ministry of the Interior) issues an OTL that is subject to prior control by the Judicial Authority (*Giudice di Pace*, Justice of the Peace) (for statistics, see page 32).

Those stopped¹⁴ within the national territory are transferred to one of the 105 local Police Headquarters Immigration Offices (*Uffici immigrazione, Questure della Polizia di Stato*) across Italian provinces. Police officers examine the background of the apprehended person to verify if they have a criminal record or if they has already applied for asylum (Interview No.4, 14/11/2023). All information is inserted into a detailed document called a *foglio notizie*. Thereafter, the local police authority (Questore) can order the issuance of an OTL to the Prefect (GNPLa, 2023). Then, the Prefect considers issuing the OTL. This procedure can, at times, become discretionary. Although the Prefect is rigidly bound by the law to carry out case-by-case assessments, the issuance of an OTL is not always automatic but requires a comprehensive assessment of the foreigner's conduct, which has wide margins of discretion. This applies, for instance, in cases of delayed submission of the application for the renewal of the residence permit by migrants who have been residing

¹² This means that rejection is deferred over time, under the following conditions (Law 40/1998, Art. 10, co. 2,): a) the foreigner has entered the territory of the State by evading border controls and is stopped at the entrance or immediately after—in a condition similar to quasi-flagrancy; b) the foreigner, despite lacking the requirements for entry, has been temporarily admitted into the territory of the State for public rescue needs. In the case of immediate rejection, the foreigner does not enter Italy, being immediately turned away at the border. In the second scenario, the foreigner crosses the border, physically enters Italian national territory, but is intercepted shortly after entry, or is admitted into Italy for rescue reasons, as in the numerous cases of landings on the Italian coasts (ASGI, 2016, p.10).

¹³ These relate to cases of foreigners who: a) are habitually engaged in criminal activities, based on factual evidence; n) by their conduct and lifestyle, are habitually living, even partially, on the proceeds of criminal activities, based on factual evidence; c) by their behaviour, are habitually committing crimes that harm or endanger the physical or moral integrity of minors, public health, safety, or tranquillity, based on factual evidence (ASGI, 2016, p.49).

¹⁴ All police forces can stop any citizen to check ID documents across Italian territory.

regularly in Italy for many years and have simply forgotten to submit their application for the renewal of their residence permit within the time limits provided by law (ASGI, 2016, p. 47).

Once an OTL is issued, the identification procedure starts for those who lack a passport. In this respect, bilateral agreements between Italy and third countries are of great importance, as well as other informal practices, as discussed in the following section.

The Importance of Bilateral Agreements in Identifying and Issuance of Travel Documents for Migrants, and Informal Practices

Cooperation between the EU and non-EU countries on the readmission of irregular migrants is considered to be instrumental in contrasting irregular migration by facilitating return procedures (Hendow et al. 2024). These measures establish clear obligations and procedures for the authorities of non-EU countries, as well as for EU member institutions involved in the return of people who have received an OTL¹⁵. In other words, such agreements can only be utilized once a return decision has been made in accordance with the Return Directive and EU asylum rules. Since 2010, the EU has concluded legally binding readmission agreements¹⁶ with Pakistan (2010), Georgia (2011), Armenia (2014), Azerbaijan (2014), Turkey (2014), Cape Verde (2014), and Belarus (2020).

Italy has also signed a series of bilateral agreements to facilitate returns¹⁷. Only few of these are part of international agreements, while most constitute Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) between Italian police authorities and those in third countries. Consequently, the content of the bilateral arrangements between police authorities is not public, unlike international bilateral agreements. MoUs have been signed between Italy and various African countries: Ghana (2010), Niger (2010), Senegal (2010), Nigeria (2011), Sudan (2016), Tunisia (2017), Gambia (2017, renewing that of 2010), Ivory Coast (2020), and Libya (2022, renewing that of 2017).

A police officer from the Ministry of the Interior highlighted the importance of such agreements in the identification and travel document issuance procedure. When readmission agreements enable the functioning of a centralised system of identification, returns can be facilitated.

In some cases involving Asian countries, such as Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Georgia, and Pakistan, identification and travel document issuance activities take place on platforms developed by the IOM through a project called EURCAP (European Readmission Capacity Building Facility). This platform involves triangulation between EU Member States, third-country national authorities and embassies, and the Ministry of the Interior. The platform can directly issue a travel document. [...] We face difficulties when there are no readmission agreements, either bilateral or at the European level. In

¹⁵ https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/irregular-migration-and-return/humane-and-effective-return-and-readmission-policy_en

¹⁶ The EU also cooperates with other non-EU countries through non-binding readmission arrangements. These are informal arrangements or deals where EU and non-EU countries fail to establish a satisfactory level of cooperation to reach a readmission agreement (Fernando-Gonzalo, 2022). In general, arrangements are easier to negotiate than readmission agreements because they are non-binding, offer more flexibility to include political commitments (such as reintegration), do not require provisions for the obligation to readmit third country nationals, allow acceptance of the EU travel document, can be customized, have less complex approval procedures in the third country, and can be kept confidential. These include arrangements with Afghanistan, Guinea, Bangladesh, Ethiopia, The Gambia, Ivory Coast. <https://www.statewatch.org/media/3680/eu-com-readmission-strategic-approach-non-paper-8429-22.pdf>

¹⁷ <https://www.meltingpot.org/2017/02/la-mappa-degli-accordi-contro-i-migranti/>

such cases, some countries may collaborate, while others may not, if there's nothing written. (Interview No.4, 14/11/2023)

However, identification and application for travel documents are generally decentralised. This means that local Police Headquarters Immigration Officers contact local diplomatic authorities (Consulates) when ID documents are missing, and the response time varies according to individual cases and third countries, as all research participants agreed. Therefore, it becomes evident that the actions and interactions of actors at the sub-national level matter. In this respect, the creation and maintenance of personal relationships between police officers and third country diplomatic services are useful tools in the return procedure. Regardless of the existence of bilateral agreements, informal practices can be of great relevance in identification and travel issuance procedures.

A phone call (to embassy or consulate personnel) every now and then to see how they (diplomatic staff) are doing... or having a coffee together and saying hello (can be) important in achieving your goal. (When dealing with third-country authorities), it's more about the right person in the right place... (Interview No.4, 14/11/2023)

When procedures of identification and travel organisation are complete, the pre-return phase begins. This approximately lasts 24 hours before the departure and include the transfer from the place where the TCN is held to the airport/port/land station. When irregular migrants are detained in a CPR, this phase also consists of the interview with the medical staff in order to acquire all necessary information about medical prescriptions and ongoing treatments. Overall, a return can take place either with or without forcible accompaniment. These procedures are discussed in the following sections.

Although MoUs with some countries facilitate return, this also depends on other factors such as the current situation in the country of return or the functioning of third-country representative in Italy. Therefore, informal diplomacy could be considered a supplementary tool where MoUs are not effective in terms of returns executions or where other factors impede execution of OTLs.

OTLs with Forcible Accompaniment to the Border

According to Directive 2008/115/EC¹⁸, “where there are no reasons to believe that this would undermine the purpose of a return procedure, voluntary return should be preferred over forced return and a period for voluntary departure should be granted”. Otherwise, as the National Guarantor for the rights of detained persons (GNPL) (GNPL, 2023a, p. 117) synopsis, return with forcible accompaniment to the border can occur under the following conditions:

- “For reasons of public order or State security (Article 13, para. 1 of the Immigration Consolidated Act), or reasons of preventing terrorist activities (Article 3, para. 1, of Decree-Law 144/2005), through ministerial expulsion,
- when there is risk of absconding (Article 13, para. 4 bis, Immigration Consolidated Act),
- when the application for a residence permit has been rejected as manifestly unfounded or fraudulent,
- when a third-country national has violated the deadline for voluntary departure without a valid justification, or one of the measures related to it (e.g. handing in passport to the police, obligation to stay in a specified residence, obligation to appear at the offices of the public security force) or related to detention in a CPR,

¹⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32008L0115>

- in the event of judicial expulsion: return as a security measure, Article 15 of the Immigration Consolidated Act, expulsion by way of substitute sanction or alternative to detention, Article 16 of the Immigration Consolidated Act, and when the expulsion has been ordered as a criminal sanction or as a consequence of a criminal sanction,
- when the third-country national has not asked to be granted voluntary departure”.

In cases of high risk, returnees can be accompanied up to their home countries by two police officers.

Detention as a Phase of a Forced Return Operation

A detention phase may be necessary for the preparation and organisation of the return (e.g., flight arrangements, verifying the irregular migrant’s ID). According to the Return Directive, this period cannot exceed six months, although it can be exceptionally extended up to 18 months.

Since 1998, Italy allowed the detention of irregular migrants of “administrative detention” structures. As a general rule, irregular migrants are held at CPRs. The recent Law 20/2023 states that the maximum duration of detention is 135 days. However, a 45-day extension can be granted when there is a forced-return agreement between Italy and the foreigner’s country of origin. In 2022, there were 10 functional CPRs across the Italian territory (Table 2): Bari, Brindisi, Caltanissetta, Rome, Potenza (Palazzo San Gervasio), Turin, Trapani, Gorizia (Gradisca d’Isonzo), Nuoro (Macomer), and Milan. Only the one in Gorizia is located at the border (with Slovenia), and the CPR in Turin is no longer functional due to extensive damage from revolts¹⁹.

Table 2 – CPRs in Italy, 2022 (Source: GNPL, 2023b, p. 195-196)

CPR	Formal (and effective) capacity	People who transited	Average days of permanence	Returned people
Bari	126 (90)	627	40.17	222
Brindisi	48 (14)	251	60.93	77
Caltanissetta	92 (72)	1,074	15.47	934
Gorizia	150 (100)	802	39.24	435
Macomer	128 (50)	202	72.74	47
Potenza	128 (90)	844	28.44	405
Rome	210 (125)	657	40.51	182
Turin	210 (140)	806	47.17	261
Trapani	205 (51)	606	16.87	400
Milan	140 (72)	457	36.87	191
Total	804	6,326	39.84	3,154

The formal capacity of CPRs does not reflect their effective capacity, largely due to a lack of human resources and poor conditions at the detention centres (GNPL, 2023b). Looking at the number of OTLs in 2018 and 2022 (see pages 28-33), detention facilities have limited capacity to host those who have received an order to leave (e.g., 815 places in relation to 27,070 return decisions issued in 2018). Claiming that detention is used to a limited extent, the actual government plans to create 12 new CPRs so that all regions will have such a facility¹⁶. However, this plan is opposed by different parts at the sub-national level. Furthermore, criticism has been systematically raised by the GNPL and third sector organisations²⁰ against the systematic use of

¹⁹ [https://roma.corriere.it/notizie/cronaca/23_settembre_24/migranti-ecco-le-nuove-regole-cpr-fondi-di-garanzia-e-centri-per-chi-arriva-da-paesi-sicuri-e970e52e-c485-4715-b6bd-5edecb9cfxlk.shtml#:~:text=Attualmente%20sul%20territorio%20nazionale%20ci,\(a%20Macomer\)%20e%20Milano.](https://roma.corriere.it/notizie/cronaca/23_settembre_24/migranti-ecco-le-nuove-regole-cpr-fondi-di-garanzia-e-centri-per-chi-arriva-da-paesi-sicuri-e970e52e-c485-4715-b6bd-5edecb9cfxlk.shtml#:~:text=Attualmente%20sul%20territorio%20nazionale%20ci,(a%20Macomer)%20e%20Milano.)

²⁰ See for instance: <https://www.asgi.it/notizie/violazioni-di-diritti-fondamentali-nel-cpr-di-trapani-il-monitoraggio-di-asgi/>; <https://www.asgi.it/allontamento-espulsione/i-diritti-umani-devono-entrare-nei-cpr/>

administrative detention instead of other measures, due to the risks involved. GNPL (2023a, p. 164) underlined that the unsuitability of premises due to poor material conditions that “do not comply with international security standards can lead to the use of force and to an intensive and generalized use of coercive measures”, while ASGI claimed that human rights are not respected in CPRs. Conversely, several regional governors, though some are supported by centre-right parties, have expressed doubts²¹ about the efficiency of such measures. In a recent interview²², Luca Zaia, the current president of the Veneto Region and a former Minister of Agriculture, stated:

“CPRs help (resolve problems connected to migration), but these are not enough, [...] these cannot resolve the problem. [...] I look at the numbers: these migrant flows should not exist. We (Italy) cannot sustain them. [...] During the last years, data say that only 8% (of newly arrived people) will access refugee status. [...] considering other forms of international protection, we can hypothesize that 30% of these people (will have a legal status). So, the reality is that at least 70% of those who arrive – arrivals should be 200,000 this year – should return. We will have to return 140,000 people. This year (2023), forced returns have been 2,270. In 2022, 3,200. The truth is that we are not able to carry out returns in a significant way. [...] It would be as if we tried to empty the sea with a pail”.

Therefore, it is unknown if this measure will be implemented given the initial reactions of regions to the creation of new CPRs. Previous research has shown that the sub-national entities (e.g., municipalities, civil society organisations, religious institutions) can shape the management of migration and asylum (Dimitriadis and Ambrosini, 2023).

Considering Table 3, some data on the reasons detained migrants leave CPRs add criticism to their functioning. Firstly, the number of detained people who effectively return to their country is only 50% of those who transit through CPRs. Secondly, for many detention is not validated by the Justice of Peace²³ (Table 3), while, thirdly, a significant number of migrants are released because the identification process fails. Fourthly, some become asylum seekers²⁴, while others are arrested inside the detention centres or are arbitrarily removed. Finally, a few die. Therefore, the usefulness of CPRs in their current form to the general aim of return is doubtful, as the risk of absconding among those released due to failed identification is high.

Table 3 - Reasons for leaving CPRs by sex, year 2022 (Source: GNPL, 2023b, p. 194)

Reason for leaving	Females	Males	Total
Arbitrarily removed	-	46	46
Arrested inside CPRs	1	49	50
Released for other reasons	2	512	514
Released because identification failed before time deadline	2	867	869
Effective returns	18	3,136	3,154
International protection applicants	4	118	122
Passed away inside CPRs	-	5	5
Not validated detention by the Judicial Authority	30	1,593	1,623
Total	57	6,326	6,383

²¹ https://www.repubblica.it/cronaca/2023/09/19/news/migranti_regioni_cpr_protesta_governatori-415094682/

²² https://www.corriere.it/politica/23_settembre_20/zaia-nuovi-centri-non-risolvono-c-tempesta-perfetta-rischiamo-crisi-sociale-37eb5160-57e8-11ee-ad09-f5d0e4dba93a.shtml

²³ When this happens, police ask the irregular migrant to leave the Italian territory within 7 days.

²⁴ Law 20/2023 has established that asylum seekers can be detained in CPRs or similar facilities for the time strictly necessary to ascertain the right to enter Italian territory (GNPL, 2023a, p. 124)

CPRs are managed by private (security) companies under the responsibility of the Prefecture of the administrative area where the centre is located. The police handle only administrative tasks related to the detainees. Additionally, third sector organisations provide services related to the well-being of migrants. In this respect, a police officer noted that the role of NGOs in executing returns can be valuable. For instance, non-profit organisations assess migrants' health conditions, which can delay or prevent return if there is a deterioration in health:

In the detention centres, Caritas or the Red Cross try to understand if there are vulnerable cases until the end of the return procedure. (Interview No.4, 14/11/2023)

There are some exemptions to detention. Those whose health conditions are incompatible with detention structure cannot be detained. In such cases, a medical examination certifies the compatibility of one's physical condition with detention. The Prefect collaborates with local public health authorities for this medical certification.

CPR is not the only structure used for detaining irregular migrants who receive an OTL. Indeed, when CPRs are full, the Justice of the Peace (*Giudice di Pace*) can authorize detention in other eligible structures, depending on the availability of the Public Security Authority. These include structures at the border where people can be detained for up to 28 days or other suitable facilities. Additionally, people can be detained at police headquarters for up to 8 days, and if necessary, up to 10 days. This practice has been highly criticized by interviewee No. 1 (13/10/2023) for concerns about respecting individual rights at police-managed locations.

Finally, alternative measures to detention include handing in passports to the police, staying in a specified residence and appearing at the offices of the public security force (GNPL, 2023a). However, these measures are rarely used. Recent studies²⁵ (see for instance CILD, 2022) and interviewees confirm this:

Alternative measures to return and detention such as the surrender of a passport and confirming presence at the police headquarters are almost totally unused. (Interview No.1, 13/10/2023)

There was a recent Schengen assessment that stated alternative measures were insufficient. This is because the ID documents (of people who receive an OTL) are few. The recommendations included applying alternative measures even when ID documents are missing. This measure is under evaluation (by Italian authorities). [...] However, in many cases, the immigration office waits for the foreigner to present himself and sign, but the foreigner does not show up. [...] An assessment on the effectiveness of the alternatives to detention - in numerical terms - is currently being discussed at national and European level. (Interview No.4, 14/11/2023)

Thus, it can be argued that migrants who receive an OTL rarely access alternatives to detention, as the police consider the risks of absconding high. This is due to the absence of a scientific assessment of such measures and measures to monitor people's presence in the territory. Overall, no relative data are available on alternative forms of detention.

²⁵ <https://www.who.int/europe/publications/i/item/9789289057929>

Orders for Voluntary Return without Forcible Accompaniment to the Border

Order for return typically require the person to voluntarily²⁶ depart from the Italian territory within a specific timeframe. Upon being stopped, an OTL is issued to the individual. State authorities are empowered to set a deadline between 7 and 30 days after the issuance of the OTL, with the possibility of extension under certain conditions.

Voluntary return carries the risk of absconding. Previous research (Dimitriadis and Ambrosini, 2022) indicates that irregular migrants, including rejected asylum seekers, who receive an OTL may choose to remain and work in Italy, thereby disobeying administrative expulsion. Alternatively, some may move to different European countries. Civil society actors such as NGOs, religious institutions, lay people and national fellows play a crucial role in assisting migrants to cope with challenges arising from their lack of legal status, including providing basic needs, legal advice and practical assistance in accessing jobs and welfare services.

Although voluntary return is not applicable to individuals with criminal records as argued above, in practice, it may still occur. According to a police officer interviewed, voluntary return may considered as a solution when it is not possible to detain people with criminal records. Yet, a shorter timeframe is provided for departure from Italian territory:

In cases involving criminal records where detention is not feasible, individuals are given a deadline of 7 days to leave the territory. (Interview No.4, 14/11/2023)

The same timeframe is also applicable to individuals who are required to leave Italian territory upon being stopped after crossing the border. However, the risk of absconding remains high, as highlighted by a research participant:

In most cases, these are orders given to third-country nationals based on deferred rejection, which are impossible to comply with. They (the police) order you (migrant) to return within 7 days. But it is assumed that migrants have a travel document, which foreign citizens very often do not posses, either because they have never had a passport, or lost it during the journey, or it has expired. and (it is also assumed) that you have the financial resources. It is evident that it is entirely impractical for the person to organize themselves to comply with that order. (Interview No.1, 13/10/2023)

Exceptions to Returns and Relative Limitations

Some exceptions apply to the right of states to deny admission to and refuse the continued presence of TCNs in their territory (ASGI, 2016; GNPL, 2023a).

1. Refugees and Asylum Seekers: According to the 1951 Geneva Convention relating to the Status of Refugees (Article 33, para. 1), “No Contracting State shall expel or return (“refouler”) a refugee in any manner whatsoever to the frontiers of territories where his life or freedom would be threatened on account of his race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group, or political opinion”²⁷. However, if there are reasonable grounds to consider refugees and asylum seekers a danger to the national security or if they have been convicted (by final judgement) of a particularly serious crime, the first paragraph of Article 33 cannot be invoked.

2. Risk of Torture or Inhuman Treatment: The prohibition of non-return also applies to individuals at risk of being subjected to torture or inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment in the state of destination. This

²⁶ On the misuse of the “voluntary” nature of return see Sahin-Mencütek and colleagues (2023).

²⁷ National law (Article 19, para. 1 of the Immigration Consolidated Act) is aligned with such provisions.

includes individuals with serious health conditions who may face significant risks due to the absence of adequate care in the return destination.

3. Unaccompanied Minors: According to the Immigration Consolidated Act (Para. 1 bis of Article 19), unaccompanied minors cannot be refused entry or deported, except in cases where they have the right to follow an expelled parent or guardian (GNPL, 2023a, p. 144). However, this exception does not apply when there are reasons of public order and state security (Article 19, para. 2 which refers to Article 13 para. 1 of the Immigration Consolidated Act).

4. Pregnant women and Recent Mothers: The same law prohibits the deportation of pregnant women or those who have given birth within the last six months (Article 19, para. 2). This ban also applies to the husband of the woman²⁸.

5. Victims of Exploitation and Violence: TCNs who have been victims of exploitation (e.g., sexual or labour exploitation), trafficking, or domestic violence, and whose situation jeopardizes their own or their family's safety, cannot be deported.

6. Natural Calamities: Temporary protection from deportation applies to individuals whose return would put their safety at risk due to natural calamities.

Overall, collective returns are generally prohibited. In addition, the right to private and family life can limit the state's ability to deport TCNs. This means that the existence of ties and connections between the TCN and host country can infringe on the repatriated person's right to private and family life (Art. 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights). Accordingly, Italian legislation stipulates that individuals cohabiting with relatives up to the second degree or with a spouse (or partner) of Italian nationality cannot be deported (Article 19 of the Immigration Consolidated Act, letter c).

Finally, aside from TCNs who may be subject to persecution for reasons of race, sex, sexual orientation, gender identity, language, citizenship, religion, political opinions, personal or social conditions and those at risk of torture or inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment after return (Article 19, para. 1 and 1 bis), in all other cases (Article 19, para 2.), exemptions cannot be applied on grounds of public order or state security (GNPL, 2023a, p. 149). In such cases, the Minister of the Interior can order the return of an irregular migrant "after informing the President of the Council of Ministers and the Minister of Foreign Affairs in advance".

Revocation and Suspension of Return Decisions

Any person who receives an OTL can appeal a return decision within 15 days²⁹ of receiving the notification or communication. This applies from the time they become fully aware of its effects. In such cases, the local Justice of Peace (*Giudice di Pace*) can:

- a) declare the appeal inadmissible;
- b) assign the appellant a deadline for regularisation, if a remediable irregularity is found;
- c) declare the appeal inadmissible, if the appellant fails to regularize their status;
- d) reject the appeal, if the Prefect recognizes the appeal as unfounded;

²⁸ Decision No. 376 of 2000 of the Constitutional Court.

²⁹ This is another change caused by Law 20/2023, as the previous term was 30 days. See <https://documenti.camera.it/leg19/dossier/pdf/D23133a.pdf>

e) accept the appeal for reasons of legitimacy or merit and annul or reform the contested act.

Appeals against an OTL issued by the Minister of the Interior for security reasons cannot suspend the return process. Additionally, if the Justice of Peace upholds the OTL, it is possible to appeal the return decision to the Supreme Court of Cassation (*Corte Suprema di Cassazione*), under certain conditions (ASGI, 2016).

Cases of appeal rarely concern OTLs issued after refusal of entry at the external border (ASGI, 2016). This is because rejection at the borders does not entail a re-entry ban to Italy or Schengen countries. Therefore, people who are refused access to the Italian territory have little interest in appealing against an OTL.

Appealing against an OTL can significantly delay or cancel the return. This is, for instance, the case when an irregular migrant applies for international protection or makes claims based on the grounds mentioned above. In the words of a police officer:

The repatriation process can be delayed or even definitively blocked if the migrant exercises a series of rights; first and foremost, the right to asylum. At the moment when the migrant, although already involved in a repatriation procedure, and already a recipient of an OTL, manifests the desire to apply for international protection, the legal situation of illegal immigrants can change: due to request for asylum, the birth of a child, a marriage to an EU or Italian citizen, or a serious health problem. (Interview No.6, 4/12/2023)

Once again, migrants appealing against OTLs are often assisted by a series of local social actors, including pro-bono lawyers, fellow nationals and civil society organisations (Dimitriadis, 2018; Dimitriadis and Ambrosini, 2022). When these cases reach the Supreme Court of Cassation and result in favourable outcomes for migrants, they can lead to changes in the legislative framework at the national level (Bonizzoni and Dimitriadis, 2024).

Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration

Although the focus of this report is on TCNs who receive an OTL, it is important to consider the provisions for assisted voluntary return and reintegration (AVRR) in the Italian case³⁰, and of the potential connections between AVRR and OTLs in practice.

TCNs who are no longer willing or able to stay in Italy can access an AVRR individual project. This project provides the necessary means for those needing to return to their country of origin. These projects are particularly available for vulnerable individuals, victims of trafficking, people holding international protection legal status, and people who fail to renew their stay permits. Eligible individuals receive:

- a) Guidance on what an AVRR project entails, including pre-departure counselling.
- b) Support such as intermediation with the diplomatic services of the TCN's country and covering the expenses for obtaining the travel document.
- c) Organization of the journey and covering the relevant costs up to the final destination, depending on the individual case.
- d) Health assistance up to the final destination.

³⁰ Ministry of the Interior - The Assisted Voluntary Return. Last access 06/10/2023. Available at: <http://www.libertaciviliimmigrazione.dlci.interno.gov.it/it/assisted-voluntary-return>

e) A first accommodation grant, provided in cash, to cover immediate costs upon return (e.g., transfers within the country), with the amount depending on individual needs.

f) Economic in-kind contributions in the country of origin to facilitate social reintegration and job placement for the final beneficiary³¹.

AVRR does not apply to individuals who have already received an OTL³². However, exceptions can be made in some cases as the following excerpts suggest:

We had many cases of migrants (project beneficiaries) who turned to us after an expulsion or multiple expulsions over time. [...] having already received an expulsion, the migrant would not have the right to stay in the Italian territory and when requesting assisted voluntary repatriation, the police headquarters very often deny it, as it is akin to acknowledging the migrant's prolonged presence in Italy despite the OTL [...] Not all Police Headquarters (enable those who receive OTLs to access AVRR)... laws are words and, as such, they are interpreted differently: some Police Headquarters in Italy are more lenient, but others are more rigid. Interview (No.5, 16/11/2023)

With the help of the psychologist or doctor, we wrote a medical, social and psychological report. And some Prefectures are willing to conduct a broader evaluation that, based on the additional documentation provided, takes into account the specific vulnerabilities that characterize the migrant at the time they request AVRR. And, in specific cases, this evaluation overturned police headquarters' decision, preventing his return (an individual who received an OTL) (thus enabling him to access AVRR). (Interview No.7, 5/12/2023)

A research participant shared their thoughts on the discretionary practices of some Police Headquarters that enable OTL recipients to access AVRR:

Regarding the police headquarters' (decisions), if I understood correctly, you mentioned that there are different interpretations, meaning this is not uniform among the police headquarters. So, the police station has to provide its opinion (on access to AVRR); it is actually a step of the procedure. [...] Perhaps, the police headquarters may have a certain margin of discretion and make their own assessments. It is a case-by-case evaluation, but general indications are certainly also given at a central level on how to orient ourselves (Prefectures and Police Headquarters). It is a case-by-case assessment, depending a bit on the individual offices, and the specific situation of the person. (Interview No.8, 6/12/2023)

This (enabling those who receive OTLs to access AVRR) depends on the open-mindedness of each Police Headquarters. We (IOM) had the possibility to revoke it (OTL) for people without a criminal record or those not considered a danger. For instance, it applied to a Ukrainian or Moldovan care worker who forgot to renew her residence permit and wished to return. (Interview No. 9, 13/12/2023)

NGOs collaborating with Police Headquarters and Prefectures to activate AVRR projects can persuade state authorities to revoke an OTL, allowing the interested person to benefit from AVRR. To do so, one of the grounds presented in pages 16-18 has to be claimed. This depends on the individual cases of OTL recipients and the discretion of local Police Headquarters or Prefectures. Discretionary power is exercised by both the

³¹ For instance, this can concern the expenses for the purchase of merchandise if the interested person is to start up a individual firm, or technological equipment if she/he intends to work in agriculture.

³² <https://integrazioneimmigranti.gov.it/it-it/Ricerca-news/Dettaglio-news/id/2021/Che-cose-il-Rimpatrio-volontario-assistito-Come-vi-si-accede>

Prefecture and Police Headquarters, two authorities that do not always align when deciding individual cases, as argued by Interviewee no. 7.

Based on this practice, it can be assumed that CPRs might be seen as places where state and non-profit organizations dealing with AVRR identify people interested in engaging in return projects. This emerges from the following quotations which highlight the importance of accessing CPRs to inform people about AVRR possibilities.

We hoped to meet those who, in our opinion, are the absolute targets most needing access (AVRR): those who have received an OTL and are found in CPRs. It would be important to create protected AVRR channels for those who are in CPRs. (Interview No.7, 5/12/2023)

For the new project (on AVRRs), we expect that information (on the possibility to access AVRR projects) will become widespread, reaching those in CPRs; and, hopefully also in prisons. In fact, we will also try to involve the social security administration. (Interview No.8, 6/12/2023)

Overall, AVRR projects seem to inspire initiatives by Frontex and Italian authorities to enhance the effectiveness of return policies (Belmonte et al. 2021). Suggesting a reintegration OTL recipients is seen as a way to improve return execution. This approach might work because people could be more inclined to return, and third-country state authorities in Italy might be more likely to cooperate in the identification procedure. In the words of a police officer:

Italy has now joined a Frontex project: we are training staff in various police stations to act as counsellors. [...] These projects bring people together to propose reintegration even in the face of a forced repatriation. [...] We have received numerous positive feedback on this. We manage to provide forms of post-arrival assistance, immediately after repatriation and post return through the NGOs that are on site in third countries (Frontex partners). [...] If I present myself at the consulate saying that a person wants to return, wants to open a business in his country and we are giving him this opportunity, the consulate is much more inclined to provide the travel document. (Interview No.4, 14/11/2023)

According to Corte dei Conti (2021) from 2016 to 2021, 3,188 people benefited from AVRR projects. However, according to EUROSTAT³³, this number is lower, with only 1,118 third-country nationals leaving Italy through assisted return.

³³ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirt_ass_custom_11901394/default/table?lang=en

Flowchart³⁴ on the return³⁵ and asylum seeking procedures, and links between the two procedures

³⁴ Elaborated by Iraklis Dimitriadis based on the flowchart in Corte dei Conti Europea (2019: p.66).

³⁵ In some cases, identification and travel document issuance also concern voluntary return.

2. Statistical description of the context

Irregular migration

While statistical data on people with legal migrant status³⁶ derive from various official sources (e.g., ISTAT, Ministry of Interior), no state organization provides data on the number of people without a residence permit. In the absence of official data the most reliable source is considered to be the ISMU Foundation, which has been making indirect evaluations³⁷ on irregular migration since 1991. In 2021, the number of migrants without any legal status was approximately 519,000, representing 9% of the total migrant population (Figure 1). First, it is interesting to note that oscillations in the number of irregular migrants might be partly connected to trends in the labour market (due to the rigid connection between formal employment contracts and residence permits) and the introduction of new regularization programs over time. For instance, it can be assumed that the decrease in the number of irregular migrants in 2012 and 2013 is due to the regularization program implemented in 2012, as highlighted above. Second, the increase in the number of irregularly staying migrants from 2015 to 2018 might be explained by the increasing number of asylum seekers, many of whom were denied regular status. Third, the further increase in the number of irregular migrants in 2018 and 2019 might be due to the introduction of a stricter legal framework regulating access to international protection (Law 13/2017 and Law 132/2018), as the number of rejected asylum seekers increased. In 2020 and 2021, irregular migration saw a decrease due to COVID-19 pandemic mobility restrictions. Therefore, quantifying the transition from the group of irregularly staying migrants to those who receive an OTL is not straightforward due to the lack of official statistics on the number of irregularly staying migrants.

Figure 1- Number of migrants in Italy (Source: ISMU)³⁸

Despite the discussion on the links between asylum seekers and irregular migration, it should be underlined that a great part of irregular migrants are visa over-stayers, mainly those whose tourist visas expire (Finotelli and Sciortino, 2013; Ambrosini, 2018). In this respect, no reliable data exist on this category. This is also confirmed by two research participants: “The great bulk of the irregular migrant historically concern over-stayers [...] but it is not easy for the authorities to register them” (Interview No.4, 14/11/2023)

³⁶ Since 2020, once migrants apply for asylum they are included in total resident population. <https://dait.interno.gov.it/servizi-demografici/circolari/circolare-n10-del-14-agosto-2020>

³⁷ For more information on the methods such evaluations are based on, see Annex 2 and Blangiardo et al. 2021.

³⁸ <https://www.ismu.org/dati-sulle-migrazioni/#1620031414351-a600237b-1828>

Eurostat also publishes data on people who are found to be illegally present in the Italian territory (Table 4). Third-country nationals found to be illegally present³⁹ are those “who are detected by Member States' authorities and have been determined to be illegally present under national laws relating to immigration. This category relates to persons who have been found to have entered illegally (for example by avoiding immigration controls or by employing a fraudulent document) and those who may have entered legitimately but have subsequently remained on an illegal basis (for example by overstaying their permission to remain or by taking unauthorised employment)”. Yet, this data does not reflect trends in the total number of irregular migrants in Italy (Figure 1). As interviewees no. 4 and 6 assume, the sharp increase in the numbers of TCNs found to be irregularly staying in Italy might be due to the fact that this data combines the number of people who receive an OTL, those who arrive in Italy by sea, and those detected at territorial borders without a passport or valid travel document .

Table 4 - Third country nationals found to be illegally present in Italy, annual (rounded), (Source: Eurostat)⁴⁰

2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
23,945	25,300	27,305	32,365	36,230	26,780	26,885	22,785	92,070	138,420	194,750

According to Eurostat, out of 138,420 (2022) and 194,750 (2023), there are 1,215 and 1,830 people, respectively, who have been found to remain in the Italian territory overstaying their visas. Yet, such data are not entirely reliable as a police officer stated. Although Italian authorities are adhering to new IT system (Entry/Exit System) that will be able to provide statistical information on over-stayers, this is not in place at the moment:

The new system will register the entry of all those who enter with a visa, even for a short duration. Where this input does not match with the output of the same within the foreseen deadlines, a report is created, let's say, a report to verify the irregularity. This tracking system will be operational throughout Europe soon. This will enable us to have a truly complete picture of this phenomenon of over-stayers. (Interview No.6, 4/12/2023)

EURODAC (2022) has recently published a report on fingerprint datasets. In 2021, Italy provided data for 64,548 people apprehended when irregularly crossing the external borders and 20,579 for those found staying illegally within the territory. Although such data are not easily usable, it is expected that the recent agreement on the core political elements of five key regulations that will thoroughly overhaul the EU's legal framework on asylum and migration⁴¹ will contribute to the development of a common database gathering more accurate and complete data to detect unauthorised movements. These EU laws cover every aspect of asylum and migration management, including the screening of irregular migrants upon arrival in the EU, the collection of biometric data, the procedures for submitting and processing asylum applications that also enhance applicants' rights, the rules for determining which member state is responsible for handling an asylum application, cooperation and solidarity between member states, and strategies for managing crisis situations, including the exploitation of migrants. Therefore, it is believed that this agreement, once adopted, will make the European asylum system more effective and enhance solidarity among member states. It is also expected that these regulations will help to ease the burden on those countries where the majority of migrants arrive.

³⁹ Eurostat explanatory texts: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/migr_eil_esms.htm

⁴⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eipre/default/table?lang=en

⁴¹ <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2023/12/20/the-council-and-the-european-parliament-reach-breakthrough-in-reform-of-eu-asylum-and-migration-system/>

Multilevel management of irregular migration and return in Italy: new insights and data
 Iraklis Dimitriadis - Deliverable on the Italian Case Study

Concerning TCNs who are refused entry at external borders, both the Ministry of the Interior and Eurostat publish relative data. However, there are inconsistencies in this case, as well.

Table 5 –Third country nationals refused entry at the external borders and Top 5 Nationalities (Source: GNPL, 2023b)

Year	Air	Sea	Land	Total	Top 5 Nationalities
2018	6,942	1,242	-	8,184	Albania 3,404 Moldavia 560 Ukraine 438 Georgia 434 Brazil 299
2019	8,138	1,805	-	9,943	Albania 4,855 Ukraine 662 Moldavia 647 Georgia 383 Brazil 352
2022	3,896	2,224	0	6,120	Albania 3,699 Moldavia 252 Georgia 240 Brazil 147 Turkey 138

Table 6 –Third country nationals refused entry at the external borders and Top 5 Nationalities (Source: Eurostat)⁴²

Year	Air	Sea	Land	Total	Top 5 Nationalities
2015	4,665	2,760	-	7,425	Albania 3,760 Moldova 510 Brazil 110 Ukraine 95 Georgia 30
2016	5,990	3,725	-	9,715	Albania 5,280 Moldova 790 Brazil 140 Ukraine 135 Georgia 30
2017	6,620	4,395	250	11,260	Albania 6,495 Moldova 700 Ukraine 205 Georgia 225 Brazil 225
2018	6,900	1,345	0	8,245	Albania 3,415 Moldova 555 Ukraine 440 Georgia 420 Brazil 285
2019	7,880	1,840	0	9,720	Albania 4,795 Moldova 620 Ukraine 655 Georgia 380 Brazil 340
2020	2,990	1,075	-	4,060	Albania 1,905 Brazil 225 Moldavia 190 Ukraine 190 Georgia 140
2021	3,550	2,180	30	5,760	Albania 3,730 Ukraine 125 Brazil 125 Moldavia 90 Georgia 70
2022	3,775	2,020	0	5,795	Albania 3,475 Moldavia 240 Georgia 225 Brazil 145 Turkey 135

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https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirfs/default/table?lang=en&category=migr.migr_man.migr_eil

Asylum Seeking

Turning to statistics concerning people who apply for asylum, it can be said that the number of asylum seekers has gradually increased from 2011 onwards (Figure 2). In 2016 and 2017, the number of asylum seekers was over 120,000, whereas this trend reversed until 2020. According to the Italian Ministry of the Interior and Eurostat, the number of people applying for international protection has increased in the last two years. Generally, it can be said that data from Eurostat⁴³ on the number of asylum seekers are slightly lower than those from the Italian Ministry of the Interior⁴⁴.

Inconsistencies in data provided by these institutions concerning the number of asylum seekers as well as forced returns, as discussed below, can be attributed to the fact that data published by Eurostat are not directly provided by the Central Directorate for Immigration and Border Police (a unified national database used by all Italian police forces). Instead, data are acquired through the Department of Civil Liberties and Immigration (Ministry of the Interior). The latter database may not be aligned and updated with data from the Statistics Office, as the database of the Department of Civil Liberties and Immigration is based on single inputs (individual entries) (GNPL, 2023a, p.175). This has also been confirmed by an officer of the Ministry of the Interior (Interview No.8, 6/12/2023).

Figure 2 – People applying for asylum in Italy (Source: Italian Ministry of the Interior, Eurostat)⁴⁵

The following figures include information on decisions regarding applications for international protection published by the Ministry of the Interior (Figure 3) and Eurostat (Figure 4). The Ministry of the Interior publishes data on cases that are labelled as “unreachable” for people who have not been contacted, and “other outcome” for cases where the application is inadmissible or when people withdraw their applications. It is unclear how this data is counted by Eurostat.

⁴⁵https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asyappctza/default/table?lang=en&category=migr.migr_asy_migr_asyapp and <https://www.interno.gov.it/it/stampa-e-comunicazione/dati-e-statistiche>

⁴⁵https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asyappctza/default/table?lang=en&category=migr.migr_asy_migr_asyapp and <https://www.interno.gov.it/it/stampa-e-comunicazione/dati-e-statistiche>

Figure 3 - Outcome of initial decisions on asylum applications (Source: Ministry of the Interior)⁴⁶

Figure 4 - Asylum applications and first instance decisions on applications (Source: Eurostat)⁴⁷

Eurostat also provides data on final decisions in appeals or reviews of applications (Table 7), which includes positive or negative decisions regarding applications for international protection, and grants of authorisations to stay for humanitarian reasons. Similar data are not published by Italian authorities.

Table 7 - Final decisions in appeal or review on applications, annual (Source: Eurostat)⁴⁸

2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
95	55	20	9,770	12,590	42,970	35,500	23,810	18,805	19,335

⁴⁶ <https://www.interno.gov.it/it/stampa-e-comunicazione/dati-e-statistiche>

⁴⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asyappctza/default/table?lang=en&category=migr.migr_asy.migr_asyapp and https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asydcfsta/default/table?lang=en&category=migr.migr_asy.migr_asydec

⁴⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asydcfina/default/table?lang=en&category=migr.migr_asy.migr_asydec

The number of international protection and humanitarian protection grants was higher than refusals from 2010 to 2014 (Figures 3 and 4). However, this trend has changed since 2015 when the number of asylum seekers increased significantly compared to previous years. In other words, the number of refusals became higher than the number of grants of international protection. Various factors have shaped trends in acceptance (green) and refusal (red) of asylum applications, as shown in Table 8:

Table 8 – Events and factors shaping trends in acceptance and refusal of asylum applications (*elaboration by Iraklis Dimitriadis*)

Event/Factor	Year	Change
Impossibility to appeal a negative asylum decision to the Court of Appeal (Law 13/2017)	Since 2017	Higher refusal
Limitation of the possibility to receive «humanitarian» protection status (Law 132/2018)	2018-2020	Higher refusal
Adoption of a list of safe countries ⁴⁹	Since 2019	Higher acceptance
Introduction of the special protection status (Law 130/2020)	Since 2020	Higher acceptance

Data on the length of the asylum procedure is limited (Corte dei Conti Europea, 2019). Neither Eurostat nor the European Union Agency for Asylum (EUAA) collect data on the length of various steps in processing asylum applications. EUAA collects limited data on delays (years) concerning the processing of pending asylum applications in the first instance, while Eurostat collects only limited data on the judicial/appeal phase. The lack of data on the length of procedures concerning asylum applications has been confirmed by various interviewees (Interviews No. 2, 4, 6, 8). Delays in the execution of OTLs are predominantly due to difficulties in identifying stopped people and processing applications for asylum among irregular migrants, as two interviewees (Interviews No.1 and 4) argued.

Returns, OTLs and Connection with Data on Irregular Migration and Asylum Seeking

Figure 5 contains information on TCNs who received an OTL and those who effectively returned. It can be observed that those who effectively return after an OTL are far fewer than those who receive an OTL. Considering OTLs and effective returns from 2017 to 2022, the ratio is approximately: 5.1:1 in 2017, 4.8:1 in 2018, 4.1:1 in 2019, 8.1:1 in 2020; 11.3:1 in 2021; and 10.1:1 in 2022. Therefore, it can be assumed that the efficiency of state authorities in removing people from Italian territory does not correspond to the increase in the number of OTLs. In addition, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the number of returned persons was very low, reflecting the mobility limitations imposed worldwide. This trend reversed in 2022, as restrictions on geographical mobility were lifted.

⁴⁹ In 2019, this list initially included: Albania, Algeria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Capo Verde, Ghana, Kosovo, Macedonia del Nord, Morocco, Montenegro, Senegal, Serbia, Tunisia and Ukraine. As highlighted above (page 8), this list was updated in 2023. https://www.asgi.it/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/decreto_paesi_sicuri.pdf

Figure 5 - Third country nationals ordered to leave Italy and effective returns (rounded) (Source: Eurostat)⁵⁰

Although Eurostat receives data on orders to leave from the Italian Ministry of the Interior, the number of OTLs is not published online. Instead, the available data published by the Ministry of the Interior pertain to effective returns (Table 9). Regarding discrepancies between data published the Italian Ministry of the Interior and Eurostat, a Police Officer (Interviewee No. 6) what argued above related to discrepancies on asylum applications (see page 26):

I can tell you that even now there are definitely discrepancies between the data published by Eurostat and the national data, despite the fact that we are the ones providing data to Eurostat. Why is this? For organizational reasons, we are still tied to providing Eurostat data through the national police database, the so-called SDI. On the other hand, with our systems, we are able to have much more precise and timely data, which, however, are not yet able to respond to all Eurostat queries. So, we are working to build an ad hoc statistical product for Eurostat that will allow us to completely abandon the use of the national police database and provide data to them directly. However, until this transition is completed, and it is a process that involves us but is not directly managed by us (there is a company that handles it), **there will always be physiological discrepancies between what Eurostat publishes and the data we have.** (Interview No.6, 4/12/2023)

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https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eiord/default/table?lang=en&category=migr.migr_man.migr_eil

Table 9 - TCNs returned following an order to leave, Italy (Source: Ministry of the Interior)⁵¹

	TCNs returned following an order to leave
2016	5,817
2017	6,514
2018	6,398
2019	6,531
2020	3,351
2021	3,420
2022	3,916

Considering values in Figures 3 and 4, another point is that the number of OTLs seems to follow the general trends in asylum applications. However, the same does not always apply to the trends characterizing the number of OTLs and the number of rejected asylum seekers, as shown in Table 10. Considering the goals of the new Pact on Migration and Asylum which promotes a common EU system to manage migration, this trend is expected to reverse⁵².

Table 10 – Relation between OTLs and negative decision on asylum application (Source: Eurostat, Ministry of the Interior, elaboration by Iraklis Dimitriadis)⁵³

Year	OTL	Change in relation to previous year (%)	Rejected Asylum Seekers	Change in relation to previous year %
2013	23,945	N/A	9,175	N/A
2014	25,300	5.7%	14,600	59.1%
2015	27,305	7.9%	41,730	185.8%
2016	32,365	18.5%	54,470	30.5%
2017	36,240	12.0%	46,440	-14.7%
2018	27,070	-25.3%	64,540	39.0%
2019	26,900	-0.6%	75,110	16.4%
2020	22,785	-15.3%	29,215	-61.1%
2021	11,095	-51.3%	21,745	-25.6%
2022	28,185	154.0%	27,385	25.9%

Regarding the type of returns, Eurostat (Figure 6) and the GNPL (based on data from the Ministry of the Interior, Figure 7) provide data that often differ. Figure 6 refers to the total number of forced returns disaggregated into forced returns (when the TCN is subject to the enforcement of the obligation to return), voluntary returns (when the TCN voluntarily complies with the obligation to return), and other types (when

⁵¹ <https://www.interno.gov.it/it/stampa-e-comunicazione/dati-e-statistiche>

⁵² https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/pact-migration-and-asylum_en

⁵³ Regarding OTLs see:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eiord/default/table?lang=en&category=migr.migr_man.migr_eil

Regarding data on Rejected Asylum seekers see: <https://www.interno.gov.it/it/stampa-e-comunicazione/dati-e-statistiche>

Changes in relation to previous year (%) are elaborations made by Iraklis Dimitriadis

some information is missing, and the departure is not confirmed by the border authority)⁵⁴. Data from the GNPL (Reports 2016-2023) (Figure 7) distinguish between accompanied and non-accompanied forced removals. This may create confusion regarding trends in returns, as it does not reflect the distinctions between forced and voluntary return according to Directive 2008/115/EC, as Eurostat data do. Once again, the number of total returns in these Figures is inconsistent (see page 26). Notably, the decline in the number of effective returns may be attributed to COVID-19 mobility restrictions.

Figure 6 - TCNs returned following an order to leave, by type of return (Source: Eurostat)⁵⁵

Figure 7 - TCNs returned following an order to leave, by type of return (Source: GNPL, 2023b and Ministry of the Interior)⁵⁶

The GNPL publishes data on the number of effective returns by province (Reports 2018, 2019, 2020, and 2023) and by type of OTL (GNPL, 2023b). Table 11 contains data on returns by type of OTL. In 2022, for instance, 1,910 out of 3,916 (48.7%) returns were executed after an OTL issued by the Prefect, 1,571 (40%) after an OTL following a border rejection, 432 (11%) after an OTL issued by judicial authorities, and only 3 after a ministerial decision (GNPL, 2023b). However, this data is difficult to use as there is no indication of the type of return that OTLs issued by prefectures and police headquarters involve.

⁵⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/migr_eil_esms.htm

⁵⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/MIGR_EIRTN1_custom_7544468/default/table

⁵⁶ <https://www.interno.gov.it/it/stampa-e-comunicazione/dati-e-statistiche>

Table 11 – Types of OTLs (Source: GNPL, 2023b)

Year	Judicial Authority	Ministry of the Interior	Prefecture	Police Headquarters	Total
2017	798	-	3,334	1,917	6,049
2022	432	3	1,910	1,571	3,916

Some data are also published on people who did not comply with an OTL requesting voluntary departure (GNPL, 2023b) by province and by OTL author. Table 12 contains data on non-compliance with return decisions by type of OTL, indicating individuals who did not return after having been asked to leave Italy voluntarily.

Table 12 - People who did not comply with an OTL (Source: GNPL, 2023b)

Year	Prefecture	Police Headquarters	Total
2017	78	387	465
2019	166	357	523
2022	76	312	388

Regarding now the characteristics of people to be returned, Figures 8 and 9 show that OTLs and effective returns predominantly concern males aged 18 to 34 and over 35. Although the content of most bilateral agreements is not public, research participants indicated that third countries do not demonstrate a preference regarding returnees' age and sex. Overall, indicators to assess the level of involvement with third countries are not easily identifiable, because bilateral agreements are often considered memoranda of understanding between police authorities and thus are inaccessible.

Figure 8 - TCNs ordered to leave - annual data, by sex and age (Source: Eurostat)⁵⁷

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https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eiord1/default/table?lang=en&category=migr.migr_man.migr_eil

Figure 9 - TCNs returned following an order to leave by sex and age (Source: Eurostat)⁵⁸

Turning to data on the nationalities of people who received an OTL and those who effectively leave Italy, Moroccans, Tunisians, Albanians, Nigerians and Egyptians are in the top five in recent years (Tables 13 and 14). Eurostat provides data both for the nationalities of those who are ordered to leave and those who effectively return. Instead, GNPL publishes ministerial data only for those who leave the Italian territory accompanied by police forces. For this reason, these datasets are not comparable.

Table 13 - Third-country nationals who have left the territory, by citizenship, OTL, and percentage of executed OTLs (Top 5 nationalities) (Source: Eurostat⁵⁹, % elaborations by Iraklis Dimitriadis)

TCN	2016			2017			2018			2019			2020		
	OTL	RET	%	OTL	RET	%									
Morocco	8,205	839	9.2	9,665	923	9.5	4,780	1,001	20.9	4,370	1,000	22.9	3,340	217	6.5
Tunisia	3,175	1,199	34.0	6,885	2,030	29.5	2,725	744	27.3	2,240	840	37.5	3,790	857	22.6
Egypt	2,030	691	45.6	1,575	387	24.6	1,215	289	23.8	1,010	350	34.7	890	91	10.2
Albania	2,270	1,035	10.2	2,330	1,179	50.6	3,035	1,379	45.4	3,225	1,531	47.5	2,630	743	28.3
Nigeria	1,820	168	19.3	2,175	345	15.9	1,960	227	11.6	2,360	389	16.5	1,760	80	4.5

⁵⁸

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eiord1/default/table?lang=en&category=migr.migr_man.migr_eil

⁵⁹

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirt_vol/default/table?lang=en&category=migr.migr_man.migr_eil

Table 14 – Third-country nationals who have left the Italian territory accompanied, by citizenship (Top 5 Nationalities) (Source: GNPL reports 2017-2023, elaborations by Iraklis Dimitriadis)

Country	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Tunisia	1,268	2,125	2,127	1,609	1,925	1,866	2,283
Egypt	691	307	148	244	66	285	322
Albania	107	186	205	261	136	167	171
Morocco	329	380	338	444	92	14	140
Nigeria	169	279	189	348	34	53	107

Considering the above tables, these nationalities reflect the composition of the entire non-EU migrant population in Italy (www.istat.it). However, the nationalities of people who receive an OTL and return are not similar to those of asylum seekers who are in the top five from 2016 to 2020⁶⁰, except for Nigerians. Regarding rejected asylum seekers (Table 15), it can be said that only Nigerians seem to be the group that increasingly receives an OTL and leaves Italy. Instead, Albanians are those who mainly return after border rejection as shown earlier (Table 12).

Table 15 – Rejected asylum seekers, (top 5 nationalities) (Source: Reports published the Ministry of the Interior)⁶¹

Country	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Nigeria	13,066	11,882	13,561	11,188	2,617
Pakistan	6,997	5,624	6,139	8,347	3,777
Gambia	5,572	3,723	4,305	3,367	467
Senegal	4,747	3,570	4,620	4,390	836
Bangladesh	4,469	3,742	7,233	6,435	1,701

To explain trends in OTLs and returns by nationality, it is also necessary to consider the nationalities of people detained in CPRs (Table 16), the existence of bilateral agreements between Italy and third countries (see page 11), as well as the list of countries considered safe until 2020 (see pages 8 and 28). First, Tunisians seem to receive particularly differentiated treatment within the hotspot system, as they are more likely than others to be considered “economic migrants” based on bilateral agreements (Calarco, 2022), and come from a safe country. Second, Morocco and Albania are also considered safe countries. All these are neighbouring countries with which Italy has traditionally developed economic and commercial ties. Fourth, trends concerning Nigerians can also be explained based on bilateral agreements.

⁶⁰ According to data published by the Ministry of the Interior, top 5 nationalities of asylum seekers (first instance) are: Nigeria, Pakistan, Gambia, Senegal, Eritrea in 2016; Nigeria, Bangladesh, Pakistan, Gambia, Senegal in 2017; Pakistan, Nigeria, Bangladesh, Senegal, Ukraine in 2018; Pakistan, Nigeria, Bangladesh, El Salvador, Peru in 2019; Pakistan, Nigeria, Bangladesh, El Salvador, Tunisia in 2020.

⁶¹ <https://www.interno.gov.it/it/stampa-e-comunicazione/dati-e-statistiche>

Table 16 – People detained in CPRs, by nationality (Source: GNPL, 2022 and 2023b)

Country	2021	% of total number of detainees	2022	% of total number of detainees
Tunisia	2,805	54.5	3,284	51.4
Egypt	515	10.0	670	10.5
Morocco	420	8.2	643	10.1
Albania	219	4.3	341	5,3
Algeria	215	4.2	205	3.2
Other	973	18.9	1,240	19.4
Total	5,147	100.0	6,383	100.0

3. Data production and loss

In the Italian case, the Ministry of the Interior is responsible for the collection, production and elaboration of data on irregularly staying migrants, OTLs and returns. Various sub-national authorities collect data on different aspects of irregular migration and return (Annex 3).

An interesting point concerns the collaboration between sub-national levels regarding the issuance of an OTL for rejected asylum seekers. Before the implementation of Law 50/2023, when a negative decision on asylum applications was made by the Territorial Commission, this was communicated to Section IV of the local Police Headquarters, responsible for international protection. Documentation on each individual case was handed from Section IV to Section III, which was responsible for the execution of OTLs. According to interviewee No, 4 (14/11/2023), this process could involve delays. However, Law 50/2023 provides that an OTL is automatically issued once a negative decision on an asylum application is made.

In light of the data provided in sections 1 and 2, (reliable) data is missing concerning:

- Visa overstayers
- Suspensions and revocations of OTLs (and reasons)
- Time concerning all procedures from the issuing of an OTL to return
- Detention of irregular migrants in other eligible structures besides CPRs
- Alternative measures to return
- Compliance of those who are invited to return voluntarily
- Re-issuing of an OTL for those who do not comply
- Temporary authorisations to stay for those whose residence permit expires

Regarding information exchange between Italian national authorities and Eurostat, inconsistencies in data arise because Eurostat does not directly communicate with the Statistics Office of the Ministry of the Interior, but with sub-Directorates collecting data on different aspects of irregular migration and returns (Annex 3).

Finally, third-sector organizations are only involved in the management of AVRR, thus being unable to provide data on OTLs and forced returns.

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Law 286/1998, Consolidated Act of Provisions concerning immigration and the condition of third country nationals (Testo Unico delle disposizioni concernenti la disciplina dell'immigrazione e norme sulla condizione dello straniero)

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Law 68/2007, People Traveling on Short-term Stay Permits for visits, business, tourism, and study (Soggiorni di breve durata degli stranieri per visite, affari, turismo e studio).

Law 129/2011, Urgent provisions for the completion of the implementation of Directive 2004/38/EC on the free movement of EU citizens and for the transposition of Directive 2008/115/EC on the return of irregular third-country nationals (Disposizioni urgenti per il completamento dell'attuazione della direttiva 2004/38/CE sulla libera circolazione dei cittadini comunitari e per il recepimento delle direttiva 2008/115/CE sul rimpatrio di cittadini di Paesi terzi irregolari),

Law 13/2017, Urgent provisions for the acceleration of procedures regarding international protection, as well as for the fight against illegal immigration (Disposizioni urgenti per l'accelerazione dei procedimenti in materia di protezione internazionale, nonché per il contrasto dell'immigrazione illegale)

Law 132/2018, Urgent Provisions on International Protection and Immigration, and Public Security (disposizioni urgenti in materia di protezione internazionale e immigrazione, sicurezza pubblica)

Law 53/2019, Urgent provisions on combating illegal immigration and on public order and security (Disposizioni Urgenti In Materia Di Contrasto All'immigrazione Illegale E Di Ordine E Sicurezza Pubblica)

Law 130/2020, Urgent provisions on immigration and security, (Disposizioni urgenti in materia di immigrazione e sicurezza)

Law 20/2023, , Urgent provisions on legal entry flows of foreign workers and the prevention and combat of irregular immigration (Disposizioni urgenti in materia di flussi di ingresso legale dei lavoratori stranieri e di prevenzione e contrasto all'immigrazione irregolare)

Annex 1 – Research participants

Interview	Role	Institution	Duration	Place	Date
No.1	Lawyer	Association for Juridical Studies on Immigration (ASGI)	30 mins.	Online	13/10/2023
No.2	Officer	Territorial Commission for the Recognition of International Protection Milan – Section I	45 mins.	Territorial Commission’s Headquarter	27/10/2023
No.3	Officer	Prefecture of Milan	20 mins.	Prefecture of Milan	27/10/2023
No.4	Police Officer	Ministry of the Interior, Public Security Dept. Central Directorate of Immigration and Border Police	74 mins.	Online	14/11/2023
No.5	Representative	CIES NGO	55 mins.	Online	16/11/2023
No.6	Police Officer	Ministry of the Interior - Department of Public Security - Central Directorate of Immigration and Border Police	28 mins.	Online	04/12/2023
No.7	Representative	CIR NGO	41 mins.	Online	05/12/2023
No.8	Officers (3)	Ministry of the Interior, Department of Civil Liberties and Immigration, Central Directorate for Civil Services concerning Immigration and Asylum	40 mins.	Online	06/12/2023
No. 9	Representative	IOM Italy	45 mins.	Online	13/12/2023

Annex 2 - Centre Sampling technique developed by the ISMU Foundation (Regional Observatory for Integration and Multiethnicity)

First estimations became possible by drawing on a report published by ISTAT in 1989, which provided an estimation of the total number of migrants present in Italy at that moment, regardless of their legal status. The difference between that number and the number of those who held a stay permit enabled the first calculation of the number of irregularly present people.

In the following years, the ISMU Foundation started to use the Centre Sampling technique to estimate the number of migrants residing irregularly in Italy. This scheme considered a local area under investigation (Provinces of Lombardy in the early 1990s), assuming that the total number of foreign citizens (both regular and irregular) present at the time of the survey was made up of N units (unknown number). The proposers of this scheme (Baio, Blangiardo and Blangiardo, 2011) also assumed that each of these individuals has some relationship with K aggregation centres or gathering places located in the area. Examples of these centers include institutions, places of worship, entertainment venues, care facilities, and meeting places. Any register of foreigners attending courses, or services, the official Population Register in a municipality, or province can be considered a "centre". The Centre Sampling scheme essentially involves 1) sampling with replacement n out of the K reference centres; 2) For each draw, one statistical unit is randomly chosen among the individuals who regularly access the selected centre.

Overall, the CS sampling technique provided a representative sample from which estimations could be derived regarding: a) the rate of foreigners (by citizenship) who were recorded, at the time of the survey, in the Official Population Register (the so called "anagrafe"), b) the rate of foreigners (by citizenship) who were in possession, at the time of the survey, of legal status with respect to residence; c) Official sources (National Statistical Institute - Istat) produce yearly the number of foreigners (by citizenship and sex) who are regularly recorded into the Official Population Register of any Italian municipality.

Example: Estimate of Ukrainian migrants in Milan on 1st July 2007

Ukrainians in the population register of Milan (residents) on 1st July 2007 = 3628

Rate of residents Ukrainians estimated on 1st July 2007 by CS sample (residents in Milan per 100 presents)= 67,5%

Rate of regular Ukrainians estimated on 1st July 2007 by CS sample (residents in Milan per 100 presents) = 79,8%

Valuation of Ukrainians in Milan on 1st July 2007 total of presents: **3,628 / 0,675 = 5375**

Of which irregular: **5,375 / (1-0,798)**

= 1086

regular not resident: **5375 - 3628 - 1086 = 661**

residents = **3628**

Annex 3 – Indicators and data collection

Indicator	Data provider	Definition	How data is collected	Frequency	Data dissemination	Corresponding Eurostat indicator (if any)	Comparability with Eurostat indicator
Irregular entry							
Refusal of entry (immediate rejection at the border)	Ministry of the Interior	Rejection at the border implies an OTL when a foreigner arrives at the border without a passport or valid travel document, and without the necessary visa.	Department of Public Security through border police	Annually	Reports published on the Website of the Ministry of the Interior Data shared with GNPL	Third country nationals refused entry at the external borders	Differences have been noted.
Deferred rejection	Ministry of the Interior	Rejection at the border is considered deferred under the following conditions (Law 40/1998, Art. 10, co. 2.): a) the foreigner has entered the territory of the State by evading border controls and is stopped at the entrance or immediately after—in a condition similar to quasi-flagrancy; b) the foreigner, despite lacking the requirements for entry, has been temporarily admitted into the territory of the State for public rescue needs.	Department of Public Security through border police	Annually	Reports published on the Website of the Ministry of the Interior Data shared with GNPL	No available data.	Not possible. Eurostat does not provide relevant data.
Irregularly staying TCN (entering the category)							
Overstayers	Ministry of the Interior	Those who may have entered legitimately but have subsequently remained on an illegal basis by overstaying their permission.	Department of Public Security	Unknown – non reliable data	Unknown – non reliable data	Third country nationals found to be illegally present	Not possible. The Ministry of the Interior does not publish relevant data.
Irregular migrants (regardless of the reason they stay irregularly in Italy)	ISMU Foundation	People without a residence permit	CS method	Annually	Annual reports published by ISMU Foundation	Third country nationals found to be illegally present in Italy	High discrepancy, mainly from 2013 to 2021
Rejected asylum seekers (first instance)	Ministry of the Interior	Those whose application to access international protection has been rejected at first instance.	Department of Civil Liberties and Immigration through Territorial Commissions and Prefectures	Published on yearly basis	Reports published on the Website of the Ministry of the Interior Data shared with GNPL	First instance decisions on applications (rejected)	Not possible. No distinction is made between first and final instance by the Ministry of the Interior.
Rejected asylum seekers (final instance)	Ministry of the Interior	Those whose reiterated application to access international protection has been rejected at final instance.	Prefectures through judicial decisions	Published on yearly basis	Reports published on the Website of the Ministry of the Interior Data shared with GNPL	Final decisions in appeal or review on applications	Not possible. No distinction is made between first and final instance by the Ministry of the Interior.
Irregular staying TCN who received OTL							
Migrants in detention centres (preremoval detention centers)	Ministry of the Interior	Irregularly staying migrants detained in CPRs	Prefectures – CPRs	Published on yearly basis	Reports published on the Website of the Ministry of the Interior Data shared with GNPL	no relevant information is available	not possible
Migrants subject to alternatives to detention	no relevant information is available	Irregularly staying migrants who receive an OTL due to having to submit their passports to the police, reside at a specified address, and report to the offices of the public security force.	no relevant information is available	no relevant information is available	no relevant information is available	no relevant information is available	not possible
Exit from the irregularly staying							

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Persons returned/readmissions	Ministry of the Interior	People who return to their country of origin, implementing an OTL	Prefectures, Border Police	Published every six months.	Reports published on the Website of the Ministry of the Interior Data shared with GNPL	Third-country nationals returned following an order to leave	Differences have been noted.
Forced returns	Ministry of the Interior	Compulsory return of an irregularly staying migrant who receive an OTL to the country of origin, transit or third country with forcible accompaniment to the border.	Prefectures, Border Police	Annually	Reports published on the Website of the Ministry of the Interior Data shared with GNPL	Third country nationals returned following an order to leave	Not possible. Data disaggregation on returns differs between the Ministry of the Interior and Eurostat.
Voluntary returns	Ministry of the Interior	When OTLs occur with forcible accompaniment to the border for where there are no reasons to believe that this would undermine the purpose of a return procedure.	Prefectures, Border Police	Annually	Reports published on the Website of the Ministry of the Interior Data shared with GNPL	Third country nationals returned following an order to leave Assisted forced return	Not possible. Data disaggregation on returns differs between the Ministry of the Interior and Eurostat.
Voluntary assisted returns	Ministry of the Interior	Return of migrants, who are no longer willing or no longer entitled to stay in Italy, with the possibility of returning to their own country of origin and of being supported in the reintegration path.	Prefectures and NGOs	Published on yearly basis	Reports published on the Website of the Ministry of the Interior Data shared with GNPL and IOM	Third-country nationals who have left the territory – assisted return	Differences have been noted.
Returns occurring under a bilateral agreement	no relevant information is available	This definition is not available.	no relevant information is available	no relevant information is available	no relevant information is available	no relevant information is available	not possible